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Pre-normative guidelines for photometric characterisation of road and pavement surfaces, including aging of road surfaces, wet conditions, mesopic visual conditions, and adaptive lighting systems (smart lighting)

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SURFACE aims at providing metrological foundations for the photometric characterisation of road surfaces in order to realise lighting systems, such as smart and adaptive lighting systems. The project is a Joint Research Project coordinated by INRiM, belonging to the European Metrology Research Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) of the European Metrology Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET). See <https://surface-nrm02.eu> for more information

SUMMARY

This document deals with guidelines for photometric characterisation of pavements, in particular under certain conditions which may affect the results and/or applicability of measurements. The first part reiterates the guidelines for measurement procedures which have been reported in project deliverable D5. These procedures are intended to be used under more or less “normal” conditions. However, there are many circumstances which requires special consideration, which is dealt with in this document.

The second part discusses the impact of aging on pavement, and deals with the impact on performance when the pavement is exposed to traffic and dirt. Guidance is provided for measurement procedure in terms of when and where to make measurement on a road. The behaviour of wet pavements is of particular interest and the state-of-the-art is reviewed.

The conditions of illuminance for road lighting installations are typical for mesopic conditions. However, despite this fact, all measurements are performed and all requirements are using using photopic quantities. The importance and impact of this is discussed in Section 4.

There are several aspects of spectral behaviour which may affect the performance of a road lighting installation, as discussed in Section 5. The different spectral power distributions of the light source may have an effect on the measured values and the measurement uncertainty.

Section 6 discusses important parameters to consider when an adaptive lighting system is used. It is common to replace existing luminaires in a road lighting installation with modern luminaires with the ability to use adaptive control. There are many aspects to consider when doing so, as detailed in this section.

The final section deals with the development of a bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) for pavement reflectance. The model can be used for photometrically realistic simulations of the pavement.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Specifications concerning road lighting and the photometry of road surfaces was established more than 40 years ago. However, pavement surface characteristics are crucial for functional quality and safety of roads, related not only to its mechanical and dynamic performance, but also to its visual performance and the safety at night of all road users. In Europe there are 5 Million kilometres of roads¹, about the 40 % of them are lit. According to three different European countries Road National Administrations, the lighting systems have been designed considering the photometric performance of pavements published in technical documents of the 1970s². Currently, road lighting installations must comply with the directives of the European Road Lighting Standards³.

Considering the physical property of the pavement, the luminance coefficient q of the road links the illuminance (linearly proportional to energy consumption) with the luminance related to the visual performance, described by a vision model which defines the luminance values required to recognize obstacles on the road. The latter is however not linearly linked to the energy consumption.

Designers determine the required number and spacing of road luminaires along a road to fulfil the requirements for road luminance and quality parameters values, given in the EN standard⁴ with the additional goal of energy optimization. To perform these calculations based on the luminance criterion, designers use reference data of r values (called r -tables) published in the CIE 144 document⁵. However, these r -tables are derived from measurements carried out more than 40 years ago. The photometric properties of the road materials have evolved over time^{6,7} and reference data is not available. Furthermore, the reliability of the data is unknown, because no statement about measurement uncertainty is presented.

The energy consumption in Europe used for lighting amounts to 14 % of the total energy consumption (data from 2011)⁸. This is the reason for the large impact on energy savings achievable with suitable actions on lighting. For road lighting, actions should start already at the design stage, by the use of more reliable and optimized q data as well as design methods specific for smart lighting.

The introduction of energy performance indicators into the European standard⁹ and its corresponding requirements pushed forward an optimization of the lighting system, not only in the design of luminaires and in the selection of their luminous intensity distribution, but also in the installation layout and in obtaining and maintaining the lighting level at the minimum value required by the standard. This last aspect can be solved by the use of adaptive lighting systems equipped with a luminance measurement system: a continuous monitoring of the road luminance can reduce the energy consumption to a minimum. The energy optimization requires reaching the luminance prescribed by road lighting standards with the lowest energy consumption. The advantages are not only in energy usage, but at lower illuminance the luminous flux reflected by the illuminated surfaces (road, buildings, grass, etc.) will be lower too, therefore the sky luminance (i.e., the lighting pollution) will be reduced.

The design of a road lighting system should be based on the knowledge of the *actual* luminance coefficient (in the direction of emission of road lighting luminaires and the direction of observation) for the actual road. Because the actual quantity of q is not known, nor is listed as reference values in the EN standard (it provides only the directions in which q should be known), designers use in the calculations as q reference values, the ones given in the CIE 144 scientific publication⁵. These values have been established from measurements on several road surfaces made in the mid-1970s and are obviously not representative of current road surfaces nor have uncertainty values. The low reliability of the available q data is well known: to be sure to reach the luminance standard requirements and avoid controversy with the customers, designers introduce an heuristic over-dimensioning of the installed luminous flux which compensates for the supposed depreciation due to ageing. These values are not adequate for designing against requirements of vision performance, optimisation and energy consumption of modern lighting installations for several reasons:

- The properties of current pavements have progressively changed, and some studies show that using the current standards, based on available CIE data, may lead to errors on average luminance often over 30 % and sometimes over 50 %¹⁰. Moreover, the photometric properties of the road materials can change significantly over time¹¹⁻¹³.

- New types of luminaires, especially those using Solid State Lighting (SSL), have very sharp luminous intensity distributions; this simplifies the energy consumption optimisation but increases the influence of the road surface reflective characteristics, especially when luminance and/or uniformity are considered.
- SSL including current LED technology supports smart lighting, and the ability to adapt the flux at any time, in terms of both intensity and direction, according to the brightness requirements and specifics of the road pavement.

It is necessary for the road lighting community to obtain new reliable standard reference values representative of present-day pavement reflectance (q and r values) with assurance of traceability of measured data. For these reasons the EU Community funded the EMPIR SURFACE project^{14,15} with the goal to establish a metrological chain for the measurement of q and r values and to provide to the European standardization body new reference tables of q and r values for currently used pavements.

This deliverable first presents quantities and practices of road lighting with a focus on road photometry. In a second part a review of available data among SURFACE project is done in accordance with the bibliography. The last part presents a comparison between reference data of CIE144 and r -tables of representative pavement surfaces measured in laboratory on samples from all over Europe and their impact on the road lighting design for typical road lighting installation layouts, e.g., those in Ref. 4.

2. GUIDELINES FOR LABORATORY AND ON-SITE MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES

2.1. SURFACE project recommendations and suggestions

In project deliverable D5 the recommendations and suggestions are detailed, see Table 1.

Table 1. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Geometries of measurement – angle of observation	<p>Extra-urban road: 1°, viewing distance of 85.9 m</p> <p>Urban road: 2.29°, viewing distance of 37.5 m</p> <p>Urban driving at low speed: 5°, viewing distance of 17 m, suitable for cycling and scooters</p> <p>Boundary between diffuse and specular behaviour: 10° and 20° are under consideration</p>
Metrological requirement for instruments for <i>r</i> -tables	<p>A measurement geometry that corresponds to the norm (observation angle) [1°, 2.29°]</p> <p>A measure that is representative of the surface (i.e. an average over enough points) [100 cm²]</p> <p>Good collimation, i.e. small angular subtense of the light source [<0.2°]</p> <p>Small detector angular subtense, i.e. good telecentricity of the detector [<0.08° cf CIE 66²]</p>
Uncertainty evaluation	<p>Good calibration of the different elements</p> <p>Determination of the values of the relevant parameters contributing to the uncertainty</p> <p>LUMCORUN software</p>
Laboratory measurement procedure	
Sample identification and extraction	<p>Reference the position of the extraction</p> <p>Avoid evident heterogenous area</p> <p>Clean the sample on-site with water after extraction (if dirt or mud introduced by the extraction process)</p> <p>Identify the circulation direction with a mark</p>
Transport and storage	<p>Place samples in conditions to maintain state</p> <p>Cover with protective material during transport</p> <p>Store samples indoors, preferably in a controlled temperature room, upside down and covered</p> <p>Do not expose samples to direct sunlight</p>

Table 1. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Alignment	<p>Ensure that the positioning of the source, sample and detector are correct with regards to each other</p> <p>The centre of the sample (P) is the centre of the measurement</p> <p>Place the surface of the sample in the reference plane, corresponding to the measured plane</p>
Recording	<p>Sample: identification code and date of extraction, condition of storage, washing actions</p> <p>Laboratory: environmental conditions including temperature and humidity, any other relevant conditions including lamp control. Depending on the type of light source used, it should be warmed-up to ensure a better stability.</p> <p>Measuring device: time of switch-on of the device (including lamp) and time of start and end of measurement, and if used, reference material used for initial setup</p>
On site measurement procedure	
Road	<p>Error! Reference source not found. shows all necessary information to be recorded about the measurement site and the road</p> <p>Road must be not used by vehicles at the time of measurement</p> <p>Environmental conditions: outside temperature above +5 °C, avoid fog</p>
Selection of the measurement area	<p>Chose a planar area without defects, use the suggested contour gauge to identify convexities</p> <p>Pavement must be dry, unsalted</p> <p>Measurement shall be done in the direction of circulation</p>
Sampling	<p>Sampling: on each lane of circulation, in the centre and in the tyre tracks.</p> <p>Choose several sampling areas and perform at least 6 measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 in the tyre track and 3 on the centre track. - If it is possible to make more measurements, it is better. - The advice is to make the same number of measurements in the tyre track and in the centre track.
Recording	<p>Place and conditions of measurement: type of road and its use, traffic, date, meteorological conditions (e.g. cloudy, sunny, windy, etc.), environmental conditions, including temperature, humidity, and dew point if available</p> <p>Type of pavement describing its general aspects (Is it dirty? Are the tyre tracks visible?) and all available information as its age, size, and colour of the granulate, type of binder, special surface treatment, etc.</p> <p>Pictures with a general view and more close-up view with a pencil or a grid to provide a size and a colour scale, including a picture with the contour gauge</p>

Table 1. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Data analysis	
Measured data and statistics	<p>Measured values depend on: heterogeneity of the surface along the road length because of the construction process and the weather exposure, type of asphalt and binder, traffic, usage, ageing, and on the measured place (centre track or tyre track).</p> <p>Avoid a mean value of the r-table, because it may not be representative of a physical surface</p> <p>Provide the most representative r-tables (considering the shape of the solid) and the extremes, i.e. three values</p> <p>Devices measuring only Q_0 and S_1, provide the mean value and standard deviation</p> <p>Possible statistical approaches:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A. Calculate the mean of all measurements and the standard deviation to quantify the road heterogeneity B. Differentiate the statistics for the centre track and tyre track: calculate the average and standard deviation for each C. Calculate a weighted average: Make a ponderation between measurement on the centre track and tyre track with a weight of 2/3 on the centre track and 1/3 on the tyre track to represent the percentage of each case on the road D. Choose an r-table which is representative of all the measurements. This last approach has the advantage of the choice of a real physical table instead of an artificial table done with the mean of all the r factors (mathematically incorrect because a weighted average is done to calculate Q_0) <p>If the classical lighting design approach is used (one typical CIE r-table with a scaling of Q_0), the measured r-table is not used but only Q_0 and S_1 factors. Thus, the average of the measured Q_0, S_1 factors could be used, using one of the preceding approaches (A, B or C). As in CIE144, the average of S_1 is used to choose the typical table and the average of Q_0 will add the scaling factor. To characterise the heterogeneity of the road, provide the mean value and also the standard deviation.</p> <p>If the actual r-table of the pavement could be used in the lighting design, it is recommended to choose a representative measured r-table instead of an average (approach D). It will provide a more physically realistic BRDF. This table is the closest from the average of the S_1 factor, makes physical sense and could be scaled according to the average of the Q_0 factor. To characterise the heterogeneity of the road, provide the mean value, and also the extremes.</p>

Table 1. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Impact of additional pavement conditions	<p>Additional influences:</p> <p>Time, traffic: the centre track is slightly darker and less specular than the tyre track</p> <p>Difficult to isolate the effect of traffic from the time and ambient conditions</p> <p>Studies show that Q_0 and S_1 are bigger in the circulated part of the road</p> <p>With salt or dust, the specularity is generally lower</p>
Spectral properties	
Influence of the sources vs spectral reflectance of pavements	<p>The design of a lighting system with RGB LED, low-pressure Sodium, high-pressure Sodium, and Xenon Pulsed is statistically more affected by the spectral behaviour of road surfaces</p> <p>The design of a lighting system equipped with LED sources, especially neutral LED (i.e. blue LED and phosphor) leads to low discrepancies (in the range -1 % to +2 %, which is half compared to the aforementioned sources)</p>

3. GUIDELINES FOR CONSIDERING ADDITIONAL ASPECTS

3.1. Impact of aging

The impact of aging on road photometry is important, especially for bituminous pavements. CIE 66² recommends to measure the road photometry after a period of not less than one year, to be more representative of the entire life of the pavement. This evolution is both due to traffic and meteorological impact.

This age effect was studied in several studies that have shown that for very thin asphalt concrete (VTAC), the specularity is higher for new pavement and decreases with time and traffic^{11,12}. Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrates this effect on several bituminous pavements. When there is an initial surface treatment, like water jet scrubbing¹², the initial specularity is lower and the pavement becomes lighter with time and traffic effect. For surface dressing, a technique used on smaller roads in France, the specularity increases with time and traffic. This evolution is caused by the shift and progressive immersion of the stones in the binder due to traffic¹¹.

A comparison with a rescaled standard *r*-table, as proposed by CIE 2001⁵ confirm that there is a big shape difference between the measurements and these standard tables¹¹.

Figure 1: Average impact of time (in months) on lightness and specularity for Very Thin Asphalt Concrete (VTAC in red) and Surface Dressing (SD in green) surfaces¹¹.

Figure 2: Average values of the photometric characteristics of four VTAC sections during the three years of study. The arrows represent the evolution of each section with time. S1 is a section composed of light stones, synthetic binder, TiO₂ adding, S2 is a treated light section, S3 is a classic bituminous section with an initial treatment. S4 is a control bituminous raw section.

Figure 3: The measurements of the Dumont French study¹¹ presented in red are compared with the corresponding scaled CIE R table in blue.

For cement concrete pavements, the impact of age is less important because their initial specularly is lower than bituminous raw pavements¹⁶. However, is illustrated in Figure 4, the heterogeneity of the photometry decreases with time and Q_0 decreases.

Figure 4. Illustration of the heterogeneity of the photometry of cement concrete pavements. The photometric measurements were done with Coluroute portable device on the new pavements (T0 in red), after 6 months (in yellow), 18 months (in green) and 30 months (in blue). The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles¹⁶. In the graph legend, the word “lane” is used instead of “track”.

In our SURFACE database, we have 240 measurements which are shown in Figure 5, considering 102 new pavements in red and the 138 pavements of more than 2-years age in orange. They are shown in comparison with the CIE standard r -tables data and an old database of 285 measurements¹⁷ done in the mid-1970s (1975) on samples mostly from the Nordic countries. Our dataset also illustrates the importance of the age affect.

Figure 5 : Representation of SURFACE database divided in new pavements in red and 2 years and older pavements in orange. The CIE standard pavements and an old database (green) of 1975¹⁷ are also presented.

To conclude, when a single characterisation of the photometry of a pavement is done, the recommendations of CIE 66² are still valid. The condition of the road surface to be measured should be representative of its state for most of its life. This means that the age of the pavement should be at least one year and even two years if possible.

Due to its exposure to traffic and meteorological conditions, the photometry of pavement changes very quickly in the first months, especially for raw pavements with bituminous binder. This specularity is really significant at a young age but, as already shown, fades fairly quickly under the effect of traffic and its exposure to climatic conditions. It is also possible to carry out a surface treatment to

The use of an initial surface treatment (shot blasting or water jet scrubbing) is useful to strip the surface bitumen film in order to stabilise the S_1 -value. It reduces the amount of variations with time and especially the initial specularity. Some light pavements also become darker with time due to the impact of dirt (oil and dust for example).

This is why it is always recommended, for better representativeness, to wait a few months before carrying out any photometric measurements.

3.2. State of the pavement considering dirt, and impact of traffic

The effects of time and traffic density can be studied with portable devices. On the slow lane, dedicated to trucks, the aspects could be different because it has the heaviest traffic. Thus, if possible, the measurements should be done on each lane of circulation, in the centre track and in the tyre track. One shall consider the tyre track in the data analysis.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 illustrate the effect of time and traffic for a concrete¹⁶ and a bituminous pavement¹⁸.

Figure 6. Illustration of the heterogeneity of the photometry of cement concrete pavements. The photometric measurements were done with Coluroute portable device on the new pavements (T0 in red), after 6 months (in yellow), 18 months (in green) and 30 months (in blue). The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles¹⁶.

Figure 7. Illustration of the age and traffic effect on a circulated typical French pavement whose photometry was measured every 6 months during 3 years with Coluroute portable device¹⁸. The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles.

In these two cases, the centre track is slightly darker and less specular than the tyre track.

The effect of ambient conditions without traffic was seldom studied and it is always difficult to isolate the effect of traffic from the time and ambient conditions.

In Fotios⁷ analysis of Cooper 2000 measurement campaign in the UK, samples were extracted on 83 places with 3 samples in each place: one in the near side (supposed as non-circulated), one in the tyre track and one in the “oil” track (supposed as in the centre track). The results were averaged by pavement type and no effect of traffic, nor “dust” was found.

A huge campaign of on-site measurements were done across New Zealand with the Memphis portable device¹⁹. There were 140 representative sites measured in autumn 2008. For each site, five measurements were taken on the shoulder (no vehicle circulation) and five on the tyre track. With this study, the effect of traffic could be studied because there is no vehicle circulation on the shoulder where half of the measurements were done.

Figure 8. Positions of the ten measurements for each site. From Ref. 19.

The pavements measured were always more than 1 year old and more than 2 years old in 92 % of the cases. There were continuous asphalt concrete, porous asphalt (called OGPA), and also surface dressing pavements (called chipseal). The effect of traffic is represented in Figure 9 for asphalt concrete (a) and surface dressing (b). It shows in both cases that Q_0 and S_1 are bigger in the circulated part of the road. Considering each site,

the specularity of the shoulder is considerably lower than the circulated part and the pavement is darker. The authors conclude that “both Q_0 and S_1 increase with traffic wear in somewhat similar proportions”.

Figure 9. Q_0 and S_1 for asphalt concrete (AC for asphalt concrete and OGPA for open graded porous asphalt) surfaces in a) and for chipseal surfaces (surface dressing) in b). The arrow shows the direction of movement from shoulder to tyre track (solid circle = shoulder value, arrowhead = tyre track value). From Ref. 19.

This effect is not so important when centre tracks and tyre tracks are compared, but is still valid.

In the presence of salt or dust, the specularity is generally lower, as illustrated in Figure 6.

3.3. Wet and dry pavements

3.3.1. Context

Lighting performance is impaired when the pavement is moist or wet. The luminance level and uniformity go down, and mirror reflection generate glare. However, road surfaces in Europe may be moist or dry a significant part of the year.

As stated in surface deliverable 5 (D5), the road photometry of a pavement shall be measured in a dry state. In the presence of moisture or water, the variations of photometry are very important, depending of the quantity of water. If the road surface is inundated, the luminance coefficients are mostly dependent on the luminance and size of the light source providing the illumination²⁰.

For wet but non-inundated surfaces, the luminance coefficients could be defined and luminance calculations are possible using reflection tables values. The “wetness” depends on the quantity of water on the surface and on the composition and texture of the pavement. The optical mechanisms are two-fold²¹:

- subscattering by water inside the material increases absorption and the material becomes darker
- reflection by the film of water covering the macrotexture is more directional and the surface appears both darker and more mirror-like.

The big problem is that "wetness" changes with time, depending on rain intensity, drainage quality, and meteorological conditions (wind, temperature, humidity) after the rain and that measurements of r -tables take time. The input of SURFACE project concerning wet pavements is a state-of-the-art review.

3.3.2. Guidelines and standards for wet road photometry

In CIE 47²² a standard wet condition was defined for a sample of road surface. The method of simulating rainfall on a road sample is described in its appendix C. The “wet condition” corresponds to a measurement done 30 minutes after having uniformly spread water at a rate of 5 mm of rain per hour in a draught-free room at a temperature of 25° and with a relative humidity of 50 %. This amount of rain has been chosen on the basis of measurements on Danish roads. They have shown that under a typical Danish weather condition, the specularly of the road surface only surpasses the slipperiness of this standard wet condition during 10 % of the time. With well drained road surfaces, this percentage is even lower.

In addition to the dry road-surface classification system, CIE 47²² also defined a classification system for wet road surfaces based on the S_1 value of the standard wet condition. As for dry tables, boundaries between WI to WIV classes are defined with the specularly S_1 value and typical tables W1 to W4 are defined with corresponding Q_0 and S_1 values (Table 2). The W classification system with its W1-W4 standard r -tables, enable luminance calculation not only for the dry condition but also for the standard wet condition. All the standard tables defined in CIE 144²³ are represented in Figure 10.

Table 2: The different classification systems defined by the CIE²³ with the name of the class defined with Latin numbers and the name of the standard tables defined with Arabic numbers to avoid confusion.

	Class name	Class limits on S_1	Class standard tables	standard Q_0	standard S_1
CIE r -table R	RI	$S_1 < 0.42$	R1	0.1	0.25
	RII	$0.42 \leq S_1 < 0.85$	R2	0.07	0.58
	RIII	$0.85 \leq S_1 < 1.35$	R3	0.07	1.1
	RIV	$1.35 \leq S_1$	R4	0.08	1.5
CIE r -table C	CI	$S_1 < 0.4$	C1	0.1	0.24
	CII	$0.4 \leq S_1$	C2	0.07	0.97
CIE r -table N	NI	$S_1 < 0.28$	N1	0.1	0.18
	NII	$0.28 \leq S_1 < 0.6$	N2	0.07	0.41
	NIII	$0.6 \leq S_1 < 1.3$	N3	0.07	0.88
	NIV	$1.3 \leq S_1$	N4	0.08	1.55
CIE r -table W	WI	$S_1 < 4.5$	W1	0.114	3.2
	WII	$4.5 \leq S_1 < 7.2$	W2	0.15	5.7
	WIII	$7.2 \leq S_1 < 9.8$	W3	0.196	8.7
	WIV	$9.8 \leq S_1 < 12$	W4	0.247	10.9

Figure 10. The different standard reflection tables for dry and wet pavements.

This classification system was established after the measurement on 205 cores of pavements in the standard wet state^{24,25}. In Figure 11, the photometric parameters (Q_0 and S_1) of these pavements is represented in their dry state in grey and in the standard wet condition in blue. For the majority of the pavements, there is a very important increase of specularity and of Q_0 in the wet condition, see Figure 12.

Figure 11. Photometric characteristics of 204 samples of pavements measured by Sorensen²⁵ in the dry condition (grey triangles) and the standard wet condition (blue circle). The CIE wet standard tables are in red diamonds.

Figure 12. Representation of the photometry of wet pavements in comparison the same pavement in its dry state for Q_0 (left) and S_1 (right). Data from Sorensen database²⁵.

Figure 13. Examples of photometry of pavements in dry condition (in red) and standard wet condition (in blue) for two class 1 and one class 3 pavements. Data from Sorensen database²⁵.

As illustrated in Figure 12 and with examples of dry and wet reflection indicatrix in Figure 13, there is no simple relation between the dry and wet state.

However, in CIE 47²² a specific specular factor S'_1 was defined for the wet condition. It was called the corrected specular factor S'_1 . It is calculated with both the S_{1wet} and Q_{0wet} factor with the following formula

$$\log\left(\frac{S'_1}{0.147}\right) = \frac{\log(S_{1wet}/0.147)}{1 - (Q_{0wet}/0.687)}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{so } S'_1 = 0.147 \times \exp\left[\frac{\log(S_{1wet}/0.147)}{1 - (Q_{0wet}/0.687)}\right]. \quad (2)$$

As shown in Figure 14, there is a linear relation between the ratio of Q_{0wet}/Q_{0dry} and S'_1 .

Figure 14. Representation of the ratio of Q_0 wet and Q_0 dry in function of S'_1 . Data from Sorensen database²⁵.

A classification system based on this corrected specular system S'_1 could be more accurate. However, since it is calculated with Q_0 and S_1 in a wet condition, it cannot be used to predict the wet photometric behaviour of a pavement from its dry state. As stated in Bommel²⁰, further investigations into wet-weather road surface conditions based on today's road surfaces are clearly needed.

The state-of-the-art review done during the SURFACE project has shown that very little research has been conducted on the photometry of wet road pavements since the eighties. The S'_1 factor is not used, probably because it depends on a wet standard state which is quite complicated to achieve.

For road marking photometry, another standard wet condition is defined in EN1436²⁶. The photometry of type II marking, which are markings visible in wet conditions could be measured 5 minutes after an exposure to a strong rain of 20 mm/h. In Burns²⁷, the wet state of road markings is produced according to ASTM E2175 standard. A measurement shall be done 1 min after the end of a simulated rain of 0.5 inch/h (12.7 mm/h). There are several methods of rain stimulations used in France, Germany and Finland that are described in Rainvision state-of-the-art report²⁸.

The amount of simulated rain is higher for road markings and the waiting time shorter, probably to take into account the slope of the road. For road photometry, the measurement is done on a flat surface with less drainage. CIE 47²² recommends a standard wetness but if the measurements take time, as is generally the case for r -tables, this is impractical.

In the standard of road lighting EN13201-2²⁹, for wet road conditions, the recommended minimal overall luminance uniformity value is 0.15.

3.3.3. State of the art of wet road photometry

In several papers, the road photometry was measured for different state of moistness.

In 1988, Basset³⁰ proposed an original approach to simulate different states of road wetness. He projected a mist of rain until saturation, which was obtained when the measured luminance reached a steady peak. Then, the spray was turned off and the luminance was monitored as a function of time at the following geometry: observation angle 1° , illumination angle $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\tan \epsilon = 5^\circ$. This experiment was used to determine two states of wetness: after 10 min and 20 min of drying. As the measurement of an r -table is a long process, it is necessary to artificially maintain the state of the sample. This was accomplished by spraying the sample with a mist, using a closed loop system consisting of a LED source, a luminance detector, and an amplifier, controlling the water flow to the

mist nozzle. The effectiveness of the stabilization method was tested by continuous observation of the luminance at $\alpha = 1^\circ$, illumination angle $\beta = 0^\circ$, $\tan \varepsilon = 5^\circ$. Four complete r -tables were measured twice with this methodology.

In 2012, Dumont²¹ wet a surface sample with a sponge so that the macrotexture was partially flooded and measured the luminance coefficient with $\alpha = 1^\circ$, illumination angle $\beta = 0^\circ$, $\tan \varepsilon = 2^\circ$. It was then possible to monitor S_1 during drying time as illustrated in Figure 15. As in Basset³⁰, a steady peak was observed both in a saturated and dry state. The question of defining wet and humid state at inflection points was raised in the communication.

Figure 15. Recording of S_1 with time when a pavement is naturally drying²¹.

In 2017 Li³¹ used a rainfall simulator according to CIE 47²² to wet road samples. The road sample was put into the wet treatment area for 15 minutes with a flow set to 5 mm per hour to become fully wet. Since rapid changes of reflection properties occur with time, a segmented measured process was defined and applied. The r -table was divided in 10 groups according to the β angle and at each time there was only a measurement of one group (corresponding to two columns of the r -table). This measurement was done in less than 30 minutes, assuming that the reflection properties would not differ much. After each group of measurements, the sample was made fully wet again and left to dry naturally for a specified duration and ready for a new set of measurements.

Figure 16. Photograph of Li wet treatment³¹ for road surface samples (left). Schematic diagram of rainfall simulator (right). ① road sample, ② splash prevention box, ③ water dropper, ④ lifting arm, ⑤ water tank, ⑥ control cabinet, ⑦ water pump.

With this methodology, it was possible to measure 20 samples of Chinese roads composed of old (O) and new (N) pavements, asphalt concrete (AC) and stone mastic asphalt (SMA). Four wet levels were defined, 'Dry', 0 minutes of drying, 30 minutes of drying (corresponding to CIE 47 standard wet condition) and 60 minutes of drying. It was shown that for all pavements both the specular reflection S_1 and Q_0 are strengthened in the wet condition and decreases with drying time. S'_1 was calculated and also decreases with drying time.

As illustrated in Figure 18, considering that the standard wet condition defined by the CIE is after 30 minutes of drying, 13 out of the 20 pavements are within WI class, 6 in WII and 1 in the WIII class.

Figure 17. Reflection indicatrix of a pavement for the four defined wet levels (From Li³¹)

Figure 18. Plot of Q_0 in function of S_1' in the standard wet condition (after 30 minutes of drying) (From Li³¹).

In 2019, Pattanapakdee³² also measured S_1 as a function of drying time starting from an inundate state. He worked on 3 different pavements with 3 samples each: a concrete pavement of 20 years, a rough asphalt sample of one year and a fine asphalt sample of two years age. Pictures of these pavements and a representation of their photometric characteristics in the dry state are presented in Figure 19. After being inundated, the evolution of S_1 with time while drying is very different between each type of pavements, see Figure 20, and differ from the other presented studies. The rough asphalt samples have very high specular factor over short time and slightly decreasing over long time. The fine asphalt and concrete samples have longer rise time and lower specular factor.

Figure 19. In the left, pictures of the pavements (a) concrete, (b) rough asphalt, (c) fine asphalt. On the right, their photometric characteristics in the dry state (From Ref. 32).

Figure 20. Evolution of the specularity factor S1 with drying time (From Ref. 32).

Ekrias³³ measured luminance on 5 sites in Finland with a video luminance photometer under various weather conditions, including dry, wet and snowy road, see Figure 21.

He has shown that the luminance of snowy road surfaces can be several times higher than in dry and so called “normal” conditions. And even if there is a minor amount of snow and snow clearance is done, luminance levels are still about 50 percent higher compared to conditions without any snow. The overall and longitudinal luminance uniformities of snowy road surfaces are usually slightly lower than in dry conditions but still adequate for the standard requirements.

In wet conditions, the luminance distributions of road surfaces change significantly compared to the dry conditions. Road surface areas with specular reflection towards the observation point become very bright and may cause discomfort glare. On the other hand, the luminance of the darker areas of the road surface decreases. This results in lower luminance uniformities and in worse driver’s visibility conditions. However, the average luminance of wet road surfaces are usually higher than in normal, dry conditions. In wet conditions on well illuminated roads the luminance of the bright areas can be over ten times higher compared to the dry conditions. When light levels are reduced, luminance levels of the bright areas are 5 to 8 times higher than in dry conditions.

The road luminance measurement results in different weather conditions show that by taking weather effects on road luminance into account, there is potential to achieve energy savings.

Figure 21. Luminance measurement results³³ measured on VT3 in Kaivoksela Finland for different road conditions: dry, partly snowy and wet road surfaces.

To conclude, it was not possible to make measurements on wet surface during our SURFACE project. However, according to the state-of-the-art review there is a need to gather more information on the subject.

4. CONCERNING MESOPIC CONDITIONS

The characterization of road lighting installations requires the measurements of luminance or illuminance using photonic quantities, but the recommended lighting levels are those typical of the mesopic vision. The link between vision conditions for safety and lighting level was correctly obtained after heuristic subjective experiments and worldwide experience³⁴, but specified using incorrect photonic quantities.

The photometric characteristics and performance of luminaires are usually specified given the emitted luminous flux, the luminous intensity distribution and the luminous efficacy, as in the European standard EN 13032³⁵. Generally, these quantities are measured considering photopic photometry. However, in many applications, as road lighting, the lighting levels are typical of the mesopic range, but also in these cases photopic quantities are traditionally used to specify the standard requirements, as in the European standard series EN 13201^{3,4,36}, to design road lighting installations or to characterize their performance.

For road lighting applications, the use of mesopic quantities for normative requirements could optimize the lighting level considering the real vision conditions and could permit an important energy saving without reducing the road safety conditions. According to the spectral luminous efficiency at the actual mesopic vision conditions, an optimization of the spectral distribution of the light emitted by luminaires could reduce the installed luminous flux and the artificial sky radiance. Unfortunately, due to the actual difficulties in identifying the observation field, the road lighting design based on mesopic quantities is not adopted in the CEN road lighting standard series. The reasons for this choice are:

- the lack of experience in the use of mesopic quantities
- the fact that the luminaire characterization does not give information to correctly calculate mesopic quantities
- the absence of proposal for algorithms aimed at calculating road lighting installation using mesopic quantities
- difficulties in the measurement of quality parameters using mesopic quantities.

The CIE recommended system³⁷ is completely defined, however, several conditions necessary for the correct evaluation of the mesopic values of lighting parameters (average luminance, uniformity, etc.) are not fully described and are still topics of research activities. Examples are the adaptation luminance that should be chosen in road lighting or the influence of glare sources (luminaires, headlamps of oncoming cars, etc.).

For the above-mentioned reasons, mesopic design is not used: some national standards try to adopt simplified approaches partially following guidelines written in CIE 206³⁸.

In the mesopic domain, however, such a gross simplification is not possible and the visual weighting function to be used cannot be defined without some knowledge of the visual adaptation conditions which, in turn, depend on the details of the light source(s) and the visual environment.

The Italian standard for the selection of lighting classes³⁹ requires a risk analysis to find the best sources for a given road situation. When the optimal lighting class is selected, if the peripheral vision is important and if the light sources have a colour rendering index R_a larger than 60, the designer may select the first class with lower performance requirements. This approach simplifies the scientific problems without considering the CIE model for mesopic vision, described in CIE 191⁴⁰.

Some papers have investigated the impact of radiance coefficient of pavement on the mesopic conditions, the main findings are in the following.

INRIM developed a method and an instrument for the in-field characterization of road lighting installations to obtain as much photometric information as possible from the lit environment. In this way it is possible to estimate the sensitivity of the evaluated parameters with respect to the spectral distribution of the seen radiation, to glare sources (luminaires or other light sources) and the adaptation luminance considering different angular extensions and conditions.

The procedure uses traditional instruments, calibrated in photonic quantities, and spectral measurement of the observed radiation to obtain the correct values of luminance or illuminance in mesopic units.

In addition, Italy has introduced some mesopic consideration for road lighting design in the selection of lighting classes, tunnel lighting is judged the most promising application field. Unfortunately, the actual application in tunnel lighting needs a database of spectral r -tables that currently is not large enough and in particular it does not include geometrical conditions fully suitable for road lighting design.

The SURFACE database highlights that only a few spectral measurements of road surface luminance coefficient are available world-wide. A larger effort to increase the spectrally tested road surfaces is necessary to ensure applicability of the mesopic design at least in a controlled environment like tunnel lighting.

4.1. Mesopic Applications in road lighting

CIE recommended a system for mesopic photometry describing spectral luminous efficiency, $V_{mes}(\lambda)$, in the mesopic region as a linear combination of the photopic spectral luminous efficiency function, $V(\lambda)$, and the scotopic spectral luminous efficiency function, $V'(\lambda)$. Since the mesopic condition of adaptation is a transient state, the CIE model describes a gradual transition between these two functions in the region of adaptation luminance between 5 cd/m^2 and $5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cd/m}^2$. Note that this is the actual range of street-lighting luminance.

For calculating mesopic luminance, the key point is the evaluation of the m value, the adaptation coefficient that can be stated or calculated considering the adaptation luminance and the S/P-ratio of the radiation. The S/P-ratio of the radiation is the ratio of the luminous output weighted with the scotopic function, $V'(\lambda)$, to the luminous output evaluated according to the photopic function, $V(\lambda)$. CIE distributed a table where the m value is stated, based on the S/P-ratio and the photopic luminance. At a photopic luminance of 5 cd/m^2 the coefficient m has a value of 1 and the mesopic luminance is therefore 5 cd/m^2 .

The design criteria for average road surface luminance in the EN recommendations fall in the range $0,3 \text{ cd/m}^2 - 2 \text{ cd/m}^2$, typically a mesopic range. Usually, the advantage of using mesopic is based on the evaluation of the S/P-ratio of the lighting source despite the difficulty of establishing the adaptation luminance. Having said this, the mesopic dimensioning favours the cool white LEDs due to the high S/P-ratio. When using the photopic dimensioning, the energy costs of an HPS lamp installation are 21 % higher than those of an LED installation, while using the mesopic dimensioning the energy costs of an HPS lamp installation are 53 % higher⁴¹. The effect of mesopic photometry increases with decreasing light level. Also, the higher the S/P-ratio, the better the light source in terms of mesopic design. At higher luminance levels of the current road lighting recommendations, the impact of mesopic photometry is small.

4.2. Relevance of spectral radiance coefficient of road surfaces

But this design approach is only based on the spectral characteristics of the lighting source and does not consider the actual spectral reflectance properties of road surfaces. Road luminance is calculated from the luminance coefficient of the road surface and the spatial luminous intensity of the luminaire

in given directions of incidence considering the observer viewing direction. To pursue mesopic design, the knowledge of spectral radiance coefficient is necessary.

Preciado and Manzano⁴² calculated the impact of spectral road surface reflectance on mesopic luminance. When the recommended system of mesopic photometry is used, light sources with S/P ratio > 1 (with a strong emission in the blue part of the visible spectrum) produce luminances higher than those calculated or measured with the photopic luminous efficiency function. On the contrary, when S/P ratio < 1 (with strong emission in the long wavelength region), mesopic luminances are lower than photopic luminances. However, in road lighting applications, as the road surface reflectance is not uniform across all visible wavelengths, the spectral power distribution (SPD) of the light coming from the light source and the SPD of the reflected light will be different. Therefore, the S/P ratio of the light coming from the road surface will be different from the S/P ratio of the light source and this will affect the calculation of the mesopic luminance, therefore also the design of the lighting system.

Preciado measured 22 samples of Argentinean roads and made calculations on the reflected luminance considering three different sources, LED, Metal Halide (MH) and High-pressure Sodium (HPS). The S/P ratio was calculated for the three sources, $S/P_{HPS} = 0,58$; $S/P_{MH} = 2,07$; $S/P_{LED} = 2,41$ and for the reflected light of the 22 road samples when lit by the above sources. As the definition of the adaptation field is the main issue in mesopic calculations, the authors chose the simplified approach of defining the adaptation field as suggested in CIE TR and TN007, considering the calculation grid of EN 13201. Introducing the spectral luminance coefficient of the road in the calculation of the mesopic road luminance, the impact of lighting source spectral mean is mitigated. Calculated values of road mesopic luminance are lower than the original S/P of the sources. This result is relevant, because other researchers considered only the impact of S/P ratio of sources⁴¹.

The knowledge of road spectral reflectance is useful for different applications, not limited to road lighting and mesopic implementation. Road surfaces can also be suitable non-variant targets or pseudo-invariant targets during the calibration/validation of remotely-sensed images⁴³. For this reason, remote sensing (imaging and hyperspectral) is widely used, in addition to on-site and laboratory spectral reflectometry.

Remote imaging spectrometry has been utilized for transportation studies, because of its ability to provide means to derive physical and chemical properties of materials, assess different pavement characteristics including age and conditions. It has also been used as reference for image calibration and validation of satellite surveys⁴⁴.

A large spectral library of road surface spectral reflectance is available online⁴⁵, typical reflection spectra show that concrete surface material exhibits the highest reflection in the visible wavelength range. Road materials like gravel and asphalt have lower reflectance, approximately 20 % and 10 %, respectively, which makes it possible to identify the pavement material used for roads. However, in the infrared wavelength range the reflectance of concrete and gravel pavements become equal at around 1 400 nm, the ratio decreasing towards longer wavelengths. This behaviour has obvious relevance in the environmental monitoring and urban heat island mitigation strategies⁴⁶

In the blue part of the spectrum (wavelengths < 500 nm), the reflectance decreases: with rapid decrease to about two times for concrete and gravel. Some measurements have shown that around 450-nm wavelength, the reflectance of concrete and gravel are even equal. The reflectance of asphalt decreases at blue wavelengths and its impact on mesopic concept application is analysed in section 3.3.1 of this document.

The large variability of spectral behaviour, shown in the data of the spectral library, is mainly due to the variability of substrates^{47,48}: asphalt pavements consist of rocky components and asphalt mix (or hot mix or bitumen). The mineral constituents of the rocky components can vary depending on the geological region, usual major components in the aggregate are SiO₂, CaO, and MgO. The asphalt mix is a complex substance that can vary in composition depending on the source of the crude oil and on the refining process.

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In brand new asphalt, the surface is completely sealed with asphalt mix and the spectral reflectance is generally low with a minimum near 350 nm, with a linear rise toward longer wavelengths. With aging reflectance increases: 10-year old asphalt reflects about twice that of 1-year old asphalt pavement. In addition to age, cracks, raveling and erosion affect the reflectance⁴⁷

Figure 22. Spectral effects of the asphalt surface characteristics of aging from the ASD ground spectral measurements (the major water-vapor absorption bands are interpolated). A, asphalt aging and erosion; B, structural road damage (cracks); C, structural road damage (raveling); D, pavement maintenance⁴⁷

In diagram B, three curves C, D, and E illustrate the effect of cracks on the reflectance of pavement. It can be seen that presence of cracks in the road pavement has an effect on spectral reflectance: high severity cracking of pavement causes reflectance decrease by about 1.5 times.

In diagram C, three curves F, G, and H depict the effect of road damage on the reflectance of pavement. It can be seen that presence of damage on the road pavement has an effect on spectral reflectance: gravel and raveling of pavement causes reflectance increase. The increase of reflectance is more pronounced in the visible part of the spectrum.

In diagram D, four curves C, I, J, and K illustrate the effect of road maintenance on the reflectance of pavement. It can be seen that spectral reflectance depends on material, as well as method of road maintenance: fresh asphalt and crack seal (curves J and I) exhibit lower reflectance as compared to that of 10-year old pavement (curve C). Chip seal of 3-years age (curve K) causes pavement reflectance to increase about 1.5 times, compared to that of 10-year old pavement (curve C).

4.3. S/P ratio of the reflected light

For the already analysed radiance coefficient pavement values, the S/P ratio of the light reflected by the pavement is calculated as the ratio between the two global luminances (photopic and scotopic) of the pavement:

$$L_V = \int_{380}^{780} E(\lambda)V(\lambda)q(\lambda)d\lambda \quad (3)$$

$$L_{V'} = \int_{380}^{780} E(\lambda)V'(\lambda)q(\lambda)d\lambda \quad (4)$$

where

L_V is the photopic luminance,

$L_{V'}$ is the scotopic luminance,

$E(\lambda)$ is the radiance, and

$q(\lambda)$ is the radiance coefficient.

$$S/P = \frac{L_V}{L_{V'}} \quad (5)$$

4.4. Mesopic measurements

4.4.1. INRIM mesopic instrument

The device measures the road surface luminance, the horizontal illuminance and the luminance of environment surfaces. At the same time, the spectral horizontal irradiance and the average spectral radiance of the road surface is measured. In this way, the common lighting parameters are obtained

and the mesopic road surface luminance or horizontal illuminance can be calculated using a conventional value of the photopic luminance of the visual adaptation field and the measured values of the S/P ratio of the incident radiation on the road surface or of the observed radiation from the road surface. When installed in the INRIM goniophotometer, it is able to measure spatial radiance distribution.

A calibrated silicon photodiode with a picoammeter is used as illuminance detector. For the spectral irradiance measurement, the scheme shown in Figure 23 is adopted. Figure 24 shows a picture of the system.

The radiation lights the detector surface of the calibrated illuminance meter. This lit surface reflects a fraction of the light, partially captured by a lens and measured by a spectrometer, connected through an optical fibre.

The system is realized using a shaped aluminium tube with a screen to stop the radiation from the unwanted hemisphere and a baffle to reduce the influence of inter-reflections between internal tube wall and the detector. The lens focuses the detector surface on the optical fibre input. At the optical fibre output, a CCD array spectrometer acquires the spectral signal. The readings of the spectrometer and the detector are synchronized and with the same integration time: this assures to measure the radiation in the same point, even if the detector is moving during the measurements.

Figure 23 The schematic of the measurement system for spectral irradiance.

Figure 24. The system installed on the INRIM goniophotometer.

The illuminance detector is a LMT photometer head AP 30 SCT with a very fine $V(\lambda)$ approximation ($f'_1 < 1\%$) calibrated using an illuminant A source. The reflectance of the opaline glass was measured considering an angle of incidence of 0° and a reflection angle of 30° corresponding to the mechanical layout of the optical system. The measurement has been carried out considering the opaline glass alone and installed in the detector. The difference between the two conditions is quite high, the ratio of the two functions has a maximum value of about 1,49 near 640 nm but the most important effect is its variability with wavelength (about 4 %), which highlights the importance to have a description of the influence of internal reflections in the detector. The radiant flux reflected by the detector filter that reaches the incidence half-space and is captured by the spectrometer lens is an important fraction of the measured light.

For the measurement of the spectral radiance of the road surface, the following approach has been adopted: a lens frames part of a lane of the carriageway on the optical fibre input of the spectroradiometer. This lens is mechanically -built-in to the lens of an ILM (Imaging Luminance Measurement Device). At the measuring distance, the portion of the road surface measured by the spectroradiometer is compared to the luminance of the same portion measured by the ILM.

The relative spectral calibration of the spectroradiometer with its lens and optical fibre is carried out using the light of a spectrally calibrated lamp reflected by a calibrated white diffusing surface.

4.4.2. Examples of measurement results with the INRIM system

In Figure 25, the relative spectral distribution of the road horizontal irradiance is shown, considering different points along the central line of the standard calculation grid of an experimental installation with only one luminaire. The variation of the spectral emission with the angle of the luminaire is clearly visible.

Considering an experimental installation with only two LED luminaires, in Figure 26 the relative spectral distribution of the road radiance in a point (first standard grid point along the central line) is shown. In this case different observation angles are considered to highlight the small influence of the observation angle in the spectral distribution of the reflected radiation, at least for the road surface of this experimental setup.

Figure 25 Example of relative spectral distribution of the horizontal irradiance.

Figure 26. Example of the relative spectral distribution of the road radiance at different observation angles.

The steps in observation angles have been chosen to compensate for the large acceptance of the system. Results highlight that the impact of the observation angle in the relative spectral distribution is not relevant: the spectral shape is conserved, so the road pavement does not show goniochromatic behaviour. This is a useful property because, if confirmed by other measurements, it opens the possibility to use pavement spectral dataset, including measurements performed in diffuse conditions or in geometries not linked to *r*-tables, for the evaluation of the global S/P ratio of the pavement reflected light. It is to note that these datasets cannot be used for road lighting design,

because the requirements on the measuring geometries, but are useful guidance for the selection of the lighting sources and mesopic impact evaluation.

5. SPECTRAL PAVEMENT BEHAVIOR

5.1. Concerning spectral impact of the lamp Spectral Power Distribution

Every light source would produce, with regards to its Spectral Power Distribution (SPD), different measured values of the luminance coefficient of pavements of non-spectrally neutral reflectance. Unfortunately, there is not a defined reference source.

Different sources are involved in the metrology of road surfaces: the lamp used for measuring the reflectance properties (on site or in laboratory) and the lamp used for the calibration of the measuring device.

From the review of currently available instruments for road surface measurements it was established that no common lighting source is generally used. Available instruments use LED sources, discharge lamps and also incandescent lamps (CIE standard illuminant A).

The SURFACE consortium investigated the impact of the instrument lighting source SPD on the luminance coefficient measured values and on the evaluated uncertainty.

5.2. Impact of source SPD on the measured values

To evaluate the impact of the SPD of the lamp used to measure the luminance coefficient, the relative luminance coefficient of a set of road surfaces of known spectral reflectance was calculated for different lighting sources.

The relative luminance coefficient C_r is defined as:

$$C_r = \frac{\int_{380}^{780} R(\lambda) \times SPD(\lambda) \times V(\lambda) \times d\lambda}{\int_{380}^{780} SPD(\lambda) \times V(\lambda) \times d\lambda} \quad (6)$$

Where:

- $V(\lambda)$: CIE spectral luminous efficiency for photopic vision (i.e. the CIE 1931 2° Standard Observer).
- $SPD(\lambda)$: Relative spectral power density of the light source normalised to its peak value.
- $R(\lambda)$: Spectral bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) of the road surface, namely the spectral luminance coefficient of the pavement for a given direction of illumination and for the geometry of observation $\alpha = 1^\circ$.

The change in the relative luminance coefficient C_r reflects the impact of the lighting source on the luminance coefficient $Q = L/E$, where L is the luminance reflected from the lighting producing the illuminance E .

In order to extend the analysis of the impact of the lighting source spectrum, a large database of 184 different lighting source spectra representing most of the available lighting technologies (LED, Metal Halide, high-pressure Sodium, low-pressure Sodium, Fluorescent, Xenon pulsed, mercury vapour, halogen) was tested on a set of nine road pavements with known spectral reflectance, see Figure 27.

Figure 27. Spectral reflectance of the test set of nine road pavements used in the calculations.

To improve the knowledge of the impact of the LED spectrum, an additional sub-set of spectra of several LED technologies have also been tested.

For each light source, the mean C_r value of the set of road surfaces was calculated, and the relative deviation of each road computed. The results are shown in Figure 28 for general lighting source, and in Figure 29 for a specific sub-set of LED sources.

a)

b)

Figure 28. a) Relative deviations of the Relative Luminance Coefficient and b) standard deviations, of the set of road surfaces for the different light sources.

a)

Figure 29. a) Relative deviations of the relative luminance coefficient of each road surface and b) standard deviations, of the set of road surfaces for different LED sources.

From the above figures, it is possible to say:

- *RGB LED, Low-pressure Sodium, High-pressure Sodium and Xenon Pulsed light sources present the largest deviations from the mean, from -3 % up to +4 %, and dispersions with respect to pavements*
- *Metal Halide (CCT = 3610 K) and Halogen (CCT = 3000 K) light sources present the lowest deviations from the mean and dispersions with respect to pavements. Absolute deviation is < 0.15 % for halogen and ≤ 0.1 % for Metal Halide.*
- *Neutral LEDs present the lowest deviations from the mean (±0.3 %) and dispersions with respect to pavements and that for all light sources, deviations are comprised in the interval [-1 %, +2 %].*

To highlight the impact of the sources on the test set, the cumulated values are shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30. Cumulated values of the different light sources on the set of road surfaces.

It is to note that these values are also useful, actually the same considerations may be applied to the inverse case; the computation of luminance values of a road of given spectral properties at the lighting design stage.

The conclusion is that:

- *The design of a lighting system with RGB LED, Low-pressure Sodium, High-pressure Sodium and Xenon Pulsed is statistically more affected by the spectral behaviour of road surfaces*
- *The design of a lighting system equipped with LED sources, especially neutral LED (i.e. blue LED and phosphor) leads to lower discrepancies (in the range -1 % to +2 %, which is half compared to the above sources)*

5.3. Impact of source SPD on the calculated uncertainty values

As said above, every light source would produce, with regards to its SPD, different measured values of the luminance coefficient of pavements of non-spectrally neutral reflectance. Currently there is no defined reference light source for measurement and every instrument has its own, relying on the calibration to compensate all spectral discrepancies. Unfortunately, detector deviations from $V(\lambda)$ and impact of SPD are not usually considered: SURFACE consortium investigated the impact on the measurement uncertainty of SPD on non-neutral road surface reflectance.

Assuming that a reference light source, of given SPD, ensures the minimum deviation on all road surfaces of the test set (Figure 27). The luminance coefficient of a pavement measured with another type of light source, other than the reference light source, will present a departure from the luminance computed with the reference coefficient, this deviation can be within the boundaries expressed by the calculations performed with a large set of lighting sources.

To establish these boundaries and observe the statistical effect of lighting SPD on the determination of the luminance coefficient, the distribution of the luminance coefficients for the test set road surface is calculated (A) for the large set of 184 light sources SPD and (B) for the reduced set where the SPD are varied by a random quantity through a basic Monte-Carlo method (MCM), see Table 3.

Table 3. Test road surface luminance coefficient boundaries for large set of 184 SPD, case A calculations.

Pavement ID	Mean Value	Standard deviation (%)	Coeff. Interval Max -Min (%)	Min (%)	Max (%)
SMA_16_W2	0.4212	0.29	2.04	-0.83	+1.22
SMA_18_L2	0.2706	0.80	5.59	-1.72	+3.87
SMA_18_L1	0.2247	0.86	5.88	-1.83	+4.05
SMA_16	0.1824	0.96	6.82	-2.10	+4.72
SMA_16_W1	0.3258	0.47	3.38	-1.31	+2.06

SMA_16_W3	0.4069	0.50	3.50	-1.47	+2.03
Ech_486	0.2538	0.28	1.96	-0.85	+1.11
Ech_822	0.1177	0.39	2.34	-0.95	+1.40
Ech_924	0.2045	0.51	3.15	-1.24	+1.91

To test the influence on the uncertainty, the SPD of a reduced set of sources was modified by a normal distribution with a standard deviation of 10 % of the peak value by MCM. The mean value, standard deviation and interval of the luminance coefficient was calculated, see Table 4.

Table 4. Luminance coefficient mean value, standard deviation and interval calculated with MCM of the variation of three given lighting sources SPD.

Lighting	_2900K_Mitsubishi		_2_1_N		Xenon_pulsed	
	SMA_16	Ech_486	SMA_16	Ech_486	SMA_16	Ech_486
Mean Value Luminance coefficient	0.182	0.254	0.182	0.254	0.178	0.252
Standard deviation (%)	0.198	0.054	0.116	0.030	0.191	0.059
Coeff. Interval (%)	0.861	0.299	0.512	0.156	0.895	0.265

The conclusion from the simulation is:

- *The SPD variations considered in the MCM simulation do not reach the large variations of luminance coefficients obtained with a large set of real lighting SPD, unless applying very strong deviations with no physical meaning*
- *Global shape changes of SPD have more impact than local variations*
- *Deviations and discrepancies depend more on the pavement characteristics, (i.e. the SMA_16 being spectrally less flat than the Ech_486 pavement) than on actual SPD variations*

6. GUIDELINES FOR ADAPTIVE LIGHTING SYSTEMS (SMART LIGHTING)

The adaptive lighting concept is defined in Ref. ⁴⁹ as “*temporal controlled changes in luminance or illuminance in relation to traffic volume (e.g. veh/5 min), time, weather or other parameters*”.

For example, adaptive road lighting installations are able to maintain constant, at the requested value, road surface luminance or illuminance despite the installation ageing, considering:

- a wide variation range of key parameters (luminous intensity depreciation of luminaire, variability of the road surface reflection properties, instability of the column voltage, etc.)
- the change of the installation lighting class according to design constraints (for example traffic volume)
- actual situation instead of hypothetical conditions linked, for example weather conditions or emergency situations.

In adaptive lighting applications, dedicated detectors are usually able to measure motor traffic volume and road average luminance. The detector permits to realize a closed-loop adaptive system which is able to select the correct lighting class according to the traffic volume, to detect weather conditions, to maintain the road luminance equal to the maintained average value required by the standard for the given lighting class, to detect anomalous situation (like the presence of vehicle queues) and if the road surface is wet.

The European standard for measuring the lighting performance of a road installation³⁶ provides requirements according to the measurement aims and in its normative annex D considers measurement systems for adaptive road lighting. To avoid technically unjustified cost for luminance measurement, the standard suggests strategies to simplify the measurement system and the operating conditions without compromising the measurement aims. The measurement uncertainty of the controlling system, evaluated considering not only the instrumental contribution but also the contribution due to installation conditions, should be considered in order to guarantee the maintained value of the photometric quality parameters as required in Ref. 9.

Usually, the detectors used in adaptive lighting are RGB cameras (ILMD), since a road surface does normally not show a selective radiometric behaviour. It is possible, using a calibrated camera, to estimate the spectral luminance coefficient of the framed road surface. Because the camera is usually installed in a geometrical position different from the CEN 2015c prescribed position (standard observer, observation angle 1°), the correlation between the road luminance considering the detector actual position and the standard observer must be obtained by calculation. Also, statistical knowledge of the road surface photometric characteristic at different angles of observation can be useful, even if it is to note that currently adaptive cameras normally frame the road from an observation point of view where the road surface behaviour is mostly Lambertian.

6.1. Adaptive system lighting installations (smart lighting)

In tunnel lighting applications, the ILMD measures during daytime the veiling luminance due to the environment outside the tunnels, i.e. the quantity correlated to the lighting level in the threshold zone of the tunnel⁵⁰. Following CIE 088:2004, the Italian standard³⁹ requires the measurement of the atmospheric luminance and of the equivalent veiling luminance to calculate the veiling luminance. The range of luminance the instrument shall measure is between 100 cd m⁻² and 20 kcd m⁻² or more at a distance from the tunnel entrance that can be as far as 350 m. Also in this situation, the instrument performance and its measurement uncertainty have a large influence on safety and management cost of the installations. During daytime, the threshold zone has the most critical requirements: a low luminance level does not guarantee the visibility of the reference object⁵⁰ while a too high level can

increase glare and discomfort. Except for very long tunnels, the threshold zone has the highest energy consumption, compared to the other zones of the tunnel, and the highest influence on installation and maintenance costs. Following the Italian standard³⁹ the average road surface luminance in the first part of the threshold zone shall not be higher than 1,5 times the minimum requirement, to maintain a safe perceived contrast of the reference object in spite of the glare⁵⁰.

In road lighting applications, ILMDs measure the road surface luminance for controlling smart adaptive road lighting systems. The instrument measures the road surface luminance in the range between $0,1 \text{ cd m}^{-2}$ and 3 cd m^{-2} ³ while the measurement distance for the normative viewing condition is about 80 m^4 . For geometrical and practical reasons (installation at about 5 m above the road surface) this distance is generally higher in real installations, e.g. up to 250 m, to approximate the condition of a viewing angle of $1^\circ \pm 0,5^\circ$ as requested by the standard⁴ and the technical report⁵. For example, with a camera height of 5,5 m, the distance should be 190 m for a viewing angle of $1,5^\circ$.

To obtain the best energy performance of an adaptive road lighting system, the system should always operate near the minimum average luminance value required by the standard, because all peculiarities linked to aging, change in reflectance behaviour (and additionally, weather and traffic) can be easily controlled and compensated for. Indeed, this approach avoid the system over-dimensioning due to high maintenance factor and poor knowledge of the road luminance coefficient.

In Figure 31, a traditional installation is compared to an adaptive solution considering for simplicity a single luminous class. The traditional installation works at constant power consumption. Its luminance decreases from the initial values to the final value, so that for a wrong estimation of the over-dimensioning, it is greater than the standard maintained value. The adaptive system works at constant luminance. Its energy consumption increases with time, but it is always lower than that of the traditional system. In this case the over-dimensioning has no consequence in the management cost. It represents a cost only in the installation phase.

Figure 31 Comparison between a traditional road lighting installation (left) and an adaptive solution (right). The luminance and the power consumption versus time of the two systems have been drawn.

6.2. Geometry setup

Usually, detectors for smart-lighting have an optical system designed to operate at given distance, generally between 50 m and about 200 m, see Figure 32. In tunnel lighting, possibly even at greater distances (up to 350 m) and the road surface luminance is obtained considering the reading of the pixels.

- To define the position of the camera of the adaptive system, several aspects must be considered:
- The observation angle is linked to the distance of the framed area and the height of the camera
- It is hard to comply with the normative requirement on observation angle ($1 \pm 0,5$)°.
- The camera can be off axis in comparison with the driver viewing direction
- The position is always a matter of balancing advantages and disadvantages related to distance, camera technical performance and environmental conditions.
- A camera with a narrow measurement cone can be used at a great distance: with a very narrow cone, it is possible to reach viewing conditions similar to the standard requirements, but the camera needs to be placed at great distance. Table 5 shows the relationship between geometry and viewing distance.

Table 5 Geometrical relationship between installation geometry and viewing angle.

Camera height	Camera distance form the framed road area	Number of luminaire pole intercepted	Camera Viewing angle
/m	/m	/1	/°
5	22	0	12,8
5	44	0	6,5
5	66	1	4,3
5	88	1	3,3
5	110	2	2,6
5	132	2	2,2
5	154	3	1,9
6	22	0	15,3
6	44	0	7,8
6	66	1	5,2
6	88	1	3,9
6	110	2	3,1
6	132	2	2,6
6	154	3	2,2
7	22	0	17,7
7	44	0	9,0
7	66	1	6,1
7	88	1	4,5
7	110	2	3,6
7	132	2	3,0
7	154	3	2,6

- For viewing conditions similar to the reference standard observer, the instrument should be placed at distances greater than 160 m, considering a typical installation height of 5 to 7 meters (to reach 1,5° of observation with a camera height of 5,5 m, the distance should be 190 m).

- This solution has the advantage of a viewing condition similar to the standard requirements ($1 \pm 0,5$)°, but has also several drawbacks:
 - the influence of the atmospheric attenuation and scattering
 - system straylight, flare and ghost images from the other luminaires and lighting sources is very critical, depending on the environmental conditions and camera performance
 - mechanical stability and accuracy in the framing area become very critical, due to environmental conditions (windy zones or great temperature range).
 - As the observation angle of the camera increases, the specular component of the reflectance of the road surface decreases and the road surface becomes like a lambertian surface. In this condition, the detector measures a luminance proportional to the illuminance on the road surface and more related to the Q_0 pavement value. All the above disadvantages have less influence, including camera technical specifications, but a deeper knowledge of pavement behaviour is needed.

Figure 32 Typical conditions of installation of a luminance measurement system.

If needed, to increase the accuracy of luminance measurements, the registered value can be multiplied by different calibration factors considering the lamp type, its correlated colour temperature and obviously the absolute luminance unit calibration coefficient.

The same sensor can also be used to measure the traffic volumes with a proprietary algorithm to count the number of vehicles in a given time interval.

6.3. Adaptive system applications in the SURFACE project

The values of road luminance coefficient q used in the design stage represent an important point for correct design of road lighting and therefore for a fruitful energy saving and rational choice of camera installation.

An adaptive system with viewing conditions similar to the standard requirements is expensive, and it can be installed only in places where environmental conditions do not systematically affect the camera readings (atmospheric impact) and position (misalignment). It is also necessary to use a camera of very high performance (straylight, flare and inter-reflection influence).

An installation setup less compliant with the standard requirements on viewing conditions is less expensive but can reach high accuracy, providing reliable and useful data too, with proper attention to detail and additional knowledge.

A camera for an adaptive lighting system control, placed at short distance from the framed road zone, has the advantage of being less sensitive to straylight and atmospheric scattering, but has the need for more knowledge of the actual road reflectance behavior. The system measures road luminance in a viewing condition not compliant with the standard but related to the road luminance coefficient measured in a different viewing geometry (or Q_0 pavement value) and road illuminance.

The analysis of the SURFACE database, made by collection of q values of current road surfaces (instead of values of road surfaces older than 30 years), show that recent pavements seem to have lower Q_0 (solid-angle weighted average luminance coefficient). Also for the median of S_1 (specular behaviour as ratio between q values at 0° and 63° of ε incidence), only a few samples have higher S_1 . Actually, in Ref. ⁵¹, the C2 reference has $Q_0=0.070$ and $S_1=0.970$, while median values of current bituminous are $Q_0=0.059$ and $S_1=0.73$, see Figure 33, orange figures from the SURFACE database.

The SURFACE project also suggests to consider some additional measurement geometry with observation angles of 10° or 20° to define the boundary condition of Lambertian behaviour.

Having current pavements with low Q_0 and S_1 values means that the specular peak has reduced width and height and the Lambertian behaviour is dominant.

Figure 33 Surface database vs CIE reference and 1975 old database.

This behavior can be useful in adaptive lighting applications since the position of the camera can hardly cope with the standard observation requirements (1°) and the link to actual road luminance may be easily established.

An additional advantage is in the camera calibration; since the condition of observation are in a region of Lambertian behavior of the pavement, the measured value depends only on the geometry of the detector (including optical system and protective case). Since SURFACE is suggesting different viewing conditions, it will be easier to link the pavement performance to the actual road luminance.

6.3.1. SURFACE impact on Geometry setup

SURFACE has established a reference test set made by some reference pavements and a reference lighting system for M2 class⁵¹.

Considering the above case of a camera installed at a short distance, not providing a viewing condition compliant with standard, for economy of the approach the camera can be positioned on the same pole as the lighting system. This means that the mounting height is limited by the installation height of the luminaire.

As said above, this condition of installation needs additional knowledge of the road surface luminance coefficient behaviour.

SURFACE proposed several additional viewing angles to take into account the viewing condition and new needs of all road users.

Since the S_1 parameter is evaluated as the ratio of the luminance coefficient at $\varepsilon = 63^\circ$ to the value at $\varepsilon = 0^\circ$, an installation geometry for the camera corresponding to a viewing angle of 63° should be avoided: it means to avoid installation distances of 10 m (for height 5 m), 12 m (for height 6 m) and 14 m (for height 7 m).

Table 6 SURFACE reference lighting system geometry.

Pole height	Pole roadside	Arm length	Pole distance
10 m	2 m	2 m	44 m

Corresponding viewing condition, the camera controlling the adaptive system should be placed in the same pole as the lighting system.

In order to minimize the effects of veiling luminance, flare and interreflection, the camera should be installed at an optimal distance from the beginning of the road grid of interest, with the minimum number of luminaires in the optical path. Table 5 shows the number of luminaires in the optical path for different camera distances.

Considering the SURFACE suggested additional viewing angles, Table 7 highlights that optimum camera performance is achieved with higher viewing angles.

Table 7 SURFACE viewing conditions vs adaptive camera geometry of installation

Camera height	Camera distance form the beginning of road area	SURFACE additional viewing conditions	Number of pole luminaire framed
/m	/m	/°	/1
5	125	2,29	3
5	57	5	1
5	28	10	1
5	14	20	0
6	150	2,29	3
6	69	5	2
6	34	10	1
6	16	20	0
7	175	2,29	4
7	80	5	2
7	40	10	1
7	19	20	0

6.4. Conclusions on Adaptive systems

The relevance of the knowledge of the road luminance coefficient is relevant at the design stage of not only road lighting systems, but also adaptive systems, where the actual values of pavement reflectance are useful for defining the design of the camera geometry setup, and for luminance calibration coefficient and data understanding.

At large viewing angles and short distances, the knowledge of Q_0 is enough, because of the Lambertian behaviour, but for comparison with the standard requirements and design values, knowledge of the road luminance coefficient is essential. If the SURFACE proposal on new angles will be accepted, having adaptive systems able to measure luminance in a standard-compliant geometry will be easily achievable. Furthermore, as shown in Ref. ⁵¹, an adaptive system or at least smart lighting control are needed when new pavements are put on a site of an existing lighting system. This is especially true when associated with new LED luminaires, because the luminaire power, with a modern pavement, needs to be rescaled to satisfy the standard requirements, bringing clear energy advantages.

In the definition of setup geometry of an adaptive system, it is not possible to define a single golden rule and a single optimal geometry. The definition is linked to the ability to compromise between camera performance, environmental conditions, accuracy needs, and pavement reflectance knowledge.

7. BEHAVIOUR MODEL OF ROAD SURFACES

7.1. Influence of the sample: building a parametric BRDF model of road pavements

7.1.1. Model introduction

The Initial BRDF model is the diffuse (Lambertian) plus the scattered specular (Phong model), as illustrated in Figure 34. The Phong model is based on the cosine of an angle elevated at a given power, this power gives the sharpness of the specular reflection; the angle of the cosine is the angle between the observation direction and the direction of the specular reflected direction. The output of this model, well used for simple physical 3D rendering engines, can be seen as a 3D-view of the r -table (not to scale). In Figure 34 is shown the intensity of reflected rays $\times \cos^3(\text{reflection angle})$, plotted for an incident ray in a spherical coordinate system (reciprocity of the r -table).

Figure 34. Lambertian diffuse and scattered specular (incident ray at 89°).

As it can be seen later, from Figure 35 and Figure 36 showing approximated road pavements, the 3D shape of the simple (Lambertian & Phong) BRDF is significantly different from real or standardized road pavements BRDF. The model can be modified with a supplementary “experimental component” which has been designed and fitted for 5 references (CIE R1, METAS sample, CIE C2, CIE R3, and CIE R4). These references have different specular index (S_1) to represent a large range of realistic BRDFs of road pavements, S_1 values are 0.25, 0.39, 0.93, 1.11, and 1.49, respectively.

7.1.2. Model development

The BRDF model is made up of the following components, with parameters adjusted manually using EXCEL:

- C1: Diffuse component (constant k_{diff})

- C2: Scattered specular component (Phong model : $k_{\text{phong}} \times (\cos(\Omega))^\alpha$), Ω = angle between specular direction and observation direction
- C3: Experimental component ($k_{\text{exp}} \times f(Y)^p \times ((\pi - \beta) / \pi)^{(1+q) \times f(Y)^2}$, with $f(Y) = \sin(Y) \times \cos(Y) / (\cos^2(Y) + k)$)
- C4: Attenuation factor for grazing angles of incidence or observation ($> 85^\circ$): function $g(Y)$ as a parametric second degree polynomial
- C5: Scattered retro-reflected component (Phong model : $k_{\text{phongr}} \times (\cos(\Omega'))^\beta$), Ω' = angle between illumination direction and observation direction

The experimental component (C3) has been designed noticing that r -tables provide superior values as $\tan(Y)$ increases and with these values being maximum in the specular direction (at $\beta = 0$) and decreasing with β with respect to the value of $\tan(Y)$. The function $f()$ is a substitute of $\tan()$ to avoid tending to infinity as the argument is tending to $\pi/2$, which cannot be seen on an r -table ($Y < 85.2^\circ$ or $\tan(Y) \leq 12$). The function is plotted in Figure 35, it tends to 0 for $Y = \pi/2$ and has a maximum at $Y = 89^\circ$. Practically for angles $< 85^\circ$ the effect on the model is the same as the tangent function.

It is observable that the METAS sample and the CIE R1 have a little retro-reflection component which has been approximated by the Phong model but not considering the angle with the specular direction but with the illumination direction. This enables a better approximation and accounts for a retro-reflection component in simulation.

The model with that component (C3) provides almost constant BRDF for different values of α . Then a supplementary component is added to the model to reflect a fast decrease as the observation/illumination angle tends to 90° , and observed in measurements (cf. METAS data in Table 8). This attenuation component does not change the fitted r -table, as it is assigned to a value of 1 under specified angles (interface input, but $< 85^\circ$) to a specified value of attenuation at 90° (interface input). Curves for some assigned values can be seen in Figure 36.

The experimental component in Excel, based on the r -table, is a function of incident angles (Y_i and β_i), to develop a complete BRDF as a function of (Θ_i , ϕ_i , Θ_r , and ϕ_r):

- For the experimental component, Y_i is transformed to $\Theta_i \times \Theta_r / \Theta_r^*$, that keeps the reciprocity of the BRDF and at $\Theta_r = \Theta_r^*$ ($\Theta_r^* = 89^\circ$ or $\alpha = 1^\circ$) yields to the values of the modelled r -table fitted with Excel. In practice, it does not change the BRDF model values very much for different Θ_r , which varies in a limited range around 89° . This component does not change too much in shape for a limited range of Θ_r around 89° , but it is multiplied by a global attenuation factor (C4) which accounts for significant BRDF changes, experimentally observed, with small variation of Θ_r as reported in Table 8. The results in Table 8 seem to indicate that the shape of the BRDF changes with a small variation of observation angle (S_1), but without detailed data it is impossible to model such behaviour.
- The experimental component β_i is transformed to $|\phi_i - \phi_r|$, which accounts for the isotropy and symmetry of the sample reflection. Note that for the r -table $\phi_r = 0$, and in the chosen coordinate system $\phi_i = \pi - \beta$, which is consistent with the fitted model with Excel.

The attenuation component is of the form $g(\Theta_i) \times g(\Theta_r)$ to keep the reciprocity, meaning it applies both for the incident angle and the observation angle as a physical effect of incident or reflected rays at grazing angles. This component will significantly change the BRDF for different α , and can be configured by the program (attenuation starting angle, attenuation at 90°), examples are shown in Figure 36. The expression of the function g is a polynomial to a given power, this power is computed depending on the desired attenuation at $\Theta_r = 90^\circ$. To keep the same BRDF values for different attenuations, the expression $g(\Theta_i) \times g(\Theta_r) / g(\Theta_r^*)$ is used in the programme. Results are presented in Table 8. The strong variations of S_1/S_2 in measurement data reflect a strong variation of BRDF with incident angles for a small variation of observation angle. This is not implemented in the model due of lack of data. The attenuation function can be adjusted through the programme interface.

Complete model 1:

$$BRDF(\Theta_i, \phi_i, \Theta_r, \phi_r) = (k_{diff} + k_{phong} \times (\cos(\Omega))^f) + k_{phongr} \times (\cos(\Omega'))^s + k_{exp} \times f(Y)^q \times ((\pi - \beta) / \pi)^{(1+q \times f(Y)^2)} \times g(\Theta_i) \times g(\Theta_r) / g(\Theta_r^*)$$

With:

$$\cos(\Omega) = \cos(\Theta_i) \times \cos(\Theta_r) - \sin(\Theta_i) \times \sin(\Theta_r) \times \cos(\phi_i - \phi_r),$$

$$\cos(\Omega') = \cos(\Theta_i) \times \cos(\Theta_r) + \sin(\Theta_i) \times \sin(\Theta_r) \times \cos(\phi_i - \phi_r),$$

$$Y = \Theta_i \times \Theta_r / \Theta_r^*$$

$$\pi - \beta = \phi_i - \phi_r$$

$g(\Theta)$: second degree polynomial to a given power, coefficients depending on the inputs: starting attenuation angle and attenuation at 90°

Θ_r^* : observation angle of fitted r -tables (here 89°)

Table 8 a) Measured data and b) simulated data with attenuation parameter at 35 %, starting angle 87.3° and CIE R3 sample.

a)

Qo difference (%)	observation angle	Q_0	S_1	S_2
-5,6	0.5°	0,187	1,342	2,256
0,0	1.0°	0,198	0,746	1,776
9,1	1.5°	0,216	0,98	1,695

b)

Qo difference (%)	observation angle	Q_0
-7,1	0.5°	0,0629
0,0	1.0°	0,0677
5,0	1.5°	0,0711

Figure 35. Modified tangent function.

Figure 36. Parametric function of attenuation at grazing angles.

The objective is not to get exactly the same *r*-table values of some references, but to provide simulation models which reflect realistic BRDFs, close to these references, for uncertainty assessment. The overall match was better than $\pm 9\%$ for 4 CIE standards and one measured sample (cf. METAS data [1]). The simulation of these 5 references constitutes, for this preliminary version, the testing BRDFs for the uncertainty assessment of geometrical effects.

The efficiency of a mathematical model is to facilitate faster computation in comparison with interpolation. Also, the 2D interpolation is not trivial and must be carefully designed, the angular variations of BRDF has a large uncertainty contribution due to aperture and misalignment effects.

The model, with components not based on physical principles, cannot be used for extrapolation at greater alpha-angles ($\alpha > 5^\circ$).

8. REFERENCES

1. Road Statistics. Yearbook 2017 Road Statistics; European Union Road Federation: Brussels, Belgium, 2017., http://www.erf.be/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Road_statistics_2017.pdf (accessed 28 March 2019).
2. *CIE 066:1984 Road surfaces and lighting (joint technical report CIE/PIARC)*. CIE, <http://cie.co.at/publications/road-surfaces-and-lighting-joint-technical-report-ciepiarc> (1984, accessed 12 March 2020).
3. EN 13201-2:2015. Road lighting - Part 2: Performance requirements.
4. EN 13201-3:2015. Road lighting - Part 3: Calculation of performance.
5. *CIE 144-2001 Road surface and road marking reflection characteristics*. Technical Report, CIE, 2001.
6. Muzet V, Colomb M, Toinette M, et al. Towards an optimization of urban lighting through a combined approach of lighting and road building activities. In: *PROCEEDINGS OF the 29th Quadrennial Session of the CIE*. Washington DC, USA: International Commission on Illumination, CIE, pp. 789–800.
7. Fotios S, Boyce P, Ellis C. The Effect of Pavement Material on Road Lighting Performance. *Light. J. Rugby*, 2006, p. 35.
8. GREEN PAPER Lighting the Future Accelerating the deployment of innovative lighting technologies, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/GA/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0889> (2011, accessed 12 March 2020).
9. EN 13201-5:2015. Road lighting - Part 5: Energy performance indicators.
10. Chain C, Lopez F, Verny P. Impact of real road photometry on public lighting design. Beijing, China: CIE, 2007.
11. Dumont E, Paumier J-L. Are standard tables r still representative of the properties of road surfaces in France? Beijing, China: CIE, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278805068_Are_standard_r-tables_still_representative_of_road_surface_photometric_characteristics_in_France (2007).
12. Muzet V, Greffier F, Nicolai A, et al. Evaluation of the performance of an optimized road surface/lighting combination: *Lighting Research & Technology* 2018; 51: 576–591.
13. Muzet V, Abdo J. On Site Photometric Characterisation of Cement Concrete Pavements with COLUROUTE Device. *Light and Engineering* 2018; 26: 88–94.
14. NRM02 SURFACE. *SURFACE*, <https://surface-nrm02.eu/> (2020, accessed 19 March 2020).
15. Iacomussi P, Rossi G, Blattner P, et al. Metrology of Road Surface for Smart Lighting. pp. 103–107.
16. Muzet V, Abdo J. On Site Photometric Characterisation of Cement Concrete Pavements with COLUROUTE Device. *Light and Engineering* 2018; 26: 88–94.
17. Sørensen K. LTL Report No. 10 Road surface reflection data.
18. Muzet V, Greffier F, Nicolai A, et al. Evaluation of the performance of an optimized road surface/lighting combination: *Lighting Research & Technology* 2018; 51: 576–591.

19. Jackett M, Frith W. Reflection properties of new zealand road surfaces for road lighting design. 2010, p. 15.
20. Bommel W van. *Road Lighting: Fundamentals, Technology and Application*. Springer International Publishing. Epub ahead of print 2015. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-11466-8.
21. Dumont E, Saint-Jacques E, Muzet V. Photometric properties of wet road surfaces.
22. CIE 047:1979 Road lighting for wet conditions, https://www.techstreet.com/cie/standards/cie-047-1979?product_id=1209979 (1979, accessed 24 December 2020).
23. *CIE 144:2001 Road Surface and Road Marking Reflection Characteristics*. CIE, 2001.
24. Frederiksen E, Sørensen K. Reflection classification of dry and wet road surfaces. *Lighting Research & Technology* 1976; 8: 175–186.
25. Sorensen K, Nielsen B. ROAD SURFACES IN TRAFFIC LIGHTING, <https://trid.trb.org/view/37817> (1974, accessed 24 December 2020).
26. EN 1436:2018 Road marking materials - Road marking performance for road users and test methods, https://standards.cen.eu/dyn/www/f?p=204:110:0:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_ORG_ID:38680,6207&cs=16797DA848BEEA8069D9DCB4A14215C2D (2018, accessed 12 March 2020).
27. Burns DM, Hodson N, Haunschild D, et al. Pavement Marking Photometric Performance and Visibility under Dry, Wet, and Rainy Conditions: Pilot Field Study. *Transportation Research Record* 2006; 1973: 113–119.
28. Diamandouros K, Nicodème C. RAINVISION State of the art.
29. EN 13201-2:2015. Road lighting - Part 2: Performance requirements.
30. Bassett MG, Dmitrevsky D, Kremer PC. Measurement of Reflection Properties of Wet Pavement Samples. *Journal of the Illuminating Engineering Society* 1988; 17: 99–104.
31. Li W, Zheng X, Zhu X, et al. Measurement system and method for reflection properties of wet road surfaces. Manchester, UK: CIE, 2017, pp. 294–302.
32. Pattanapakdee K, Chotigo S. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF PAVEMENT LIGHT REFLECTION CHARACTERISTICS IN WET CONDITIONS. In: *PROCEEDINGS OF the 29th Quadrennial Session of the CIE*. Washington DC, USA: International Commission on Illumination, CIE, pp. 1790–1795.
33. Ekrias A, Eloholma M, Halonen L. Analysis of Road Lighting Quantity and Quality in Varying Weather Conditions. *LEUKOS* 2007; 4: 89–98.
34. M. Etienne, A. Fisher, P. Hautala, et al. *CIE 093:1992 Road Lighting As An Accident Countermeasure*. CIE 093-1992, Vienna, 1992.
35. EN 13032-1:2004. *Light and lighting - Measurement and presentation of photometric data of lamps and luminaires - Part 1: Measurement and file format*. 1st ed. Brussels, Belgium: CEN, 2004.
36. EN 13201-4:2015. Road lighting - Part 4: Methods of measuring lighting performance.
37. CIE 191:2011. *Recommended System for Mesopic Photometry Based on Visual Performance*. CIE Central Bureau, 2010.

38. Fotios, S., Goodman, T., Völker, S. *CIE 206:2014 The Effect Of Spectral Power Distribution On Lighting For Urban And Pedestrian Areas*. CIE 206:2014, Vienna, 2014.
39. UNI 11431:2011. Luce e illuminazione - Applicazione in ambito stradale dei dispositivi regolatori di flusso luminoso (Light and Lighting – Use of luminous flux controllers in road lighting).
40. L. Halonen, M. Puolakka, M. Ayama, et al. *CIE 191:2010 Recommended System For Mesopic Photometry Based On Visual Performance*. CIE 191:2010, Vienna, 2010.
41. Ylinen A-M, Puolakka M, Halonen L. Road surface reflection properties and applicability of the R-Tables for today's pavement materials in Finland. *Light and Engineering*, 2010, pp. 78–90.
42. Preciado O, Manzano E. Spectral characteristics of road surfaces and eye transmittance: Effects on energy efficiency of road lighting at mesopic levels. *Lighting Research & Technology* 2018; 50: 842–861.
43. Mei A, Salvatori R, Fiore N, et al. Integration of Field and Laboratory Spectral Data with Multi-Resolution Remote Sensed Imagery for Asphalt Surface Differentiation. *Remote Sensing* 2014; 6: 2765–2781.
44. Novack T, Esch T, Kux H, et al. Machine Learning Comparison between WorldView-2 and QuickBird-2-Simulated Imagery Regarding Object-Based Urban Land Cover Classification. *Remote Sensing* 2011; 3: 2263–2282.
45. Santa Barbara Asphalt Road Spectral Library, http://www.geo-informatie.nl/Projects/Santa_Barbara_Urban_Spectral_Library/urbanspec/road_spec.htm (accessed 24 September 2020).
46. Rossi G, Iacomussi P, Zinzi M. Lighting Implications of Urban Mitigation Strategies through Cool Pavements: Energy Savings and Visual Comfort. *Climate* 2018; 6: 26.
47. Herold M, Roberts D. Spectral characteristics of asphalt road aging and deterioration: implications for remote-sensing applications. *Appl Opt* 2005; 44: 4327.
48. Herold M, Roberts DA, Gardner ME, et al. Spectrometry for urban area remote sensing—Development and analysis of a spectral library from 350 to 2400 nm. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 2004; 91: 304–319.
49. *CEN/TR 13201-1:2014. Road lighting - Part 1: Guidelines on selection of lighting classes*. CEN, 2014.
50. W. Adrian, A. Augdal, M. Bizjak, et al. CIE 088:2004 Guide for the lighting of road tunnels and underpasses, 2nd ed.
51. Gidlund H, Lindgren M, Muzet V, et al. Road Surface Photometric Characterisation and Its Impact on Energy Savings. *Coatings* 2019; 9: 286.